

LHC

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LHC-TC-EC-0010

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ENGINEERING CHANGE REQUEST

Replacement of one Primary Crystal Collimator (TCPC) in IR7

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED CHANGE(S):

Four crystal primary (TCPC) collimators are installed in IR7 for collimation studies. The LS1 installation of 2 crystals for Beam 1 was complemented in the EYETS 2016 by 2 new crystals for Beam 2. The latter used a new generation of goniometers and improved the crystal bending angles. It is proposed to replace one TCPC with a new one during the YETS 2017. This possibility could only be finalized after beam measurements at the LHC that took place at the end of the 2017 Run. The final decision depends also on the availability of a new crystal that was finally tested in the H8 line by the UA9 collaboration in mid-December 2017. For any choice of the TCPC to be replaced, the proposed intervention would entail minimal layout changes as the new crystal would replace an existing one with no modification of the adjacent vacuum components.

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SUMMARY OF THE ACTIONS TO BE UNDERTAKEN:

Note: When approved, an Engineering Change Request becomes an Engineering Change Order.
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1. EXISTING SITUATION AND INTRODUCTION

Crystal collimation is being studied as a possible improvement of the LHC collimation system for HL-LHC. Bent crystals might be used as primary collimators (TCPs) to channel halo particles onto a single collimator absorber, as opposed to the present TCP that scatter halo particles onto several secondary collimators. This scheme is particularly interesting for heavy-ion beam collimation.

During LS1, two crystals were installed on Beam 1 in the betatron cleaning insertion (IR7), one in the horizontal (in 4L7) and one in the vertical (in 6L7) direction [1]. These crystals are mounted each on a goniometer that is used to adjust their position and angle with respect to the circulating beams. During standard LHC operation, the goniometers are not visible to the beam as they are retracted and "shielded" by a special round vacuum chamber that offers to the beam a smooth aperture. We call this crystal/goniometer assembly TCPC, for Target Collimator Primary Crystal.

During the Extended Year-End Technical Stop in 2016 (EYETS 2016), two new crystals were installed also for Beam 2 at equivalent positions [2]. The Beam 2 crystals also use an improved goniometer technology. The EYETS 2016 intervention left untouched the Beam 1 setup that presents some non-conformities in the crystal bending angles.

One more goniometer is presently available at CERN. It is being used for laboratory controls tests. It is proposed to improve further the LHC installations by replacing one of the TCPC with a new one.

The possibility to perform this installation is subject to the availability of one crystal of better quality than the ones presently installed (e.g., better bending angle or channeling efficiency). This possibility was assessed by the UA9 collaboration through beam tests in the H8 beam line. The final decision on the possible replacement of a TCPC was also subject to the results of beam tests planned in Machine Development (MD) time at the LHC that will assess the properties of the 4 crystals presently available. It was initially expected that a final decision could be taken by October 2017. Because of changes of LHC schedule, the relevant MD block was moved at the very end of the run (early December 2017), which delayed the final decision. The final H8 run could only take place in mid-December.

After December 2017 MD data analysis, it has been decided to replace the TCPCH.A5R7.B2 crystal collimator by a new one holding a new PNPI strip-crystal.

2. REASON FOR THE CHANGE

The replacement of one crystal in the LHC was considered as an improvement of the present layout in preparation for the 2018 run when tests with ion beams are planned. The results of 2017 MDs at the LHC indicated that one of the newly installed crystal assembly in Beam 2-Horizontal did not perform as expected. The suspected cause of this problem is an issue with the alignment that puts the crystal too close to "skew planes" [3]. In this condition, channeling was observed but the orientation is not ideal for collimation cleaning studies. It is therefore proposed to replace this crystal with a new one (instead of what was tentatively planned initially, i.e. to upgrade one of the B1 TCPCs).

It is proposed to replace the TCPCH.A5R7.B2 crystal collimator. The new device will use a new goniometer compliant to the bake-out requirements and will mount a new strip-crystal built by PNPI.

The new goniometer for this installation will be of the latest generation that resolved vacuum non-conformities of the LS1 goniometers, which limited the baking temperature to below 150 °C because of the limitation of the piezo-electric sensor. With some adaptations of the mechanics (details depend on the chosen slot), this new goniometer might be installed in any of the 4 locations presently occupied by crystals.

3. DETAILED DESCRIPTION

The design of the goniometers that hold the bent crystals relies on movable vacuum chambers that hide the crystals from the circulating beam in standard operation. In the OUT position, a round chamber of the same size of the adjacent chambers – 80 mm diameter – is seen by the beam (see Figure 1). The IN position is only allowed with safe beam intensities [1].

The new goniometer will replace one presently installed, TCPCH.A5R7.B2, with essentially no required modification of the vacuum layout in the area. The presently used controls cables will be re-used for the new TCPC, so no new cabling campaign is necessary.

The design of the new goniometer incorporates a spring-loaded system that ensures permanent contact thanks to a spacer that pre-loads the piezo actuator. The solution has been validated through several lab tests and bake-out cycles. As a result, the new goniometer to replace the currently installed in TCPCH.A5R7.B2 is fully bake able.

Figure 1 — Schematic drawing of the horizontal goniometer setup: the crystal can be inserted into the beam only when the C-shape replacement chamber is moved out (on the bottom in the figure).

The 3D reference corresponding to the crystal collimator in the horizontal configuration is the ST0563346_01.

4. IMPACT ON OTHER ITEMS

4.1 IMPACT ON ITEMS/SYSTEMS

LHC collimation system	The proposed installation adopts the quick-installation concept for an easier integration into the collimation system.
BE/BI	The present BLM system required not further modifications in case of a TCPC replacement. The possibility to improve the present diamond BLM acquisition for fast loss measurements is also under evaluation (optional). This would provide bunch-by-bunch measurements at crystal locations.
Machine protection	No change of the present controls chain for the connection to the machine protection system.
BE/OP	The new device will have to be properly configured in the top level control layer of LSA.
TE/VSC	No impact on the adjacent vacuum components.

4.2 IMPACT ON UTILITIES AND SERVICES

Raw water:	No.
Demineralized water:	No.
Compressed air:	No.
Electricity, cable pulling (power, signal, optical fibres...):	No.
DEC/DIC:	No.
Racks (name and location):	No.
Vacuum (bake outs, sectorisation...):	The new goniometer is of the last generation that is fully bake-able. Its installation will be subject to the approval from the VSC team, following the usual criteria for leaks and outgassing.
Special transport/handling:	The crystal/goniometer assembly is extremely delicate, and shall be transported, installed and aligned similarly to the recommendations of document [1] written for the goniometers previously installed on B1.
Temporary storage of conventional/radioactive components:	-
Alignment and positioning:	After installation, the new goniometer should be properly fiducialized by the Survey team.
Scaffolding:	Not needed.
Controls:	The possibility to make the controls compatible with un-safe beam intensity is being considered for the 2018 operation. This will be formally presented to the collimation/machine protection panels. This change, if taking place, would only have impacts on EN/STI as the connection to the machine protection system will remain unchanged. Operations with higher intensity than the setup limit of

	3x10 ¹¹ charges will obviously be subject to approval of the proposed procedure by the relevant panels (LSWG and MPP).
GSM/WIFI networks:	-
Cryogenics:	No.
Contractor(s):	N/A
Surface building(s):	N/A
Others:	

5. IMPACT ON COST, SCHEDULE AND PERFORMANCE

5.1 IMPACT ON COST

Detailed breakdown of the change cost:	Most of the hardware is already at CERN so the budget implications involve only installation costs. The new crystal is provided by the UA9 collaboration.
Budget code:	HL-LHC-WP5 code 61072

5.2 IMPACT ON SCHEDULE

Proposed installation schedule:	Installation toward the end of the YETS2017 for ALARA. No impact on the overall YETS2017 schedule.
Proposed test schedule (if applicable):	Prior to installation: control test (EN/STI), vacuum validation (TE/VSC), fiducialization (EN/ACE).
Estimated duration:	<1 week installation time (without taking into account activity from other teams i.e. BE/BI and EN/ACE-SU).
Urgency:	--
Flexibility of scheduling:	Flexible. Hardware/controls expected to be ready by early 2018.

5.3 IMPACT ON PERFORMANCE

Mechanical aperture:	No impact as the new hardware is the same in this respect.
Impedance:	<p>The layout with replacement chamber has been already evaluated and approved by the impedance team. No problems were observed for the high-intensity operation when the installed goniometers on Beam 1 and Beam 2 in their OUT position.</p> <p>Studies are ongoing to assess if the new goniometer design in the IN position can be compatible also with operation at higher intensities, but, in the absence of beam tests with more nominal bunches and agreement between simulations and bench RF measurements, it is assumed for now that the goniometers in IN position are not compatible with nominal LHC beam intensities.</p>
Optics/MADX	-

Electron cloud (NEG coating, solenoid...)	-
Insulation (enamelled flange, grounding...)	-
Vacuum performance:	-
Others:	-

6. IMPACT ON OPERATIONAL SAFETY

6.1 ÉLÉMENT(S) IMPORTANT(S) DE SECURITÉ

Requirement	Yes	No	Comments
EIS-Access		X	-
EIS-Beam		X	-
EIS-Machine		X	-

6.2 OTHER OPERATIONAL SAFETY ASPECTS

Have new hazards been created or changed?	No.
Could the change affect existing risk control measures?	No.
What risk controls have to be put in place?	None.
Safety documentation to update after the modification	-
Define the need for training or information after the change	-

7. WORKSITE SAFETY

7.1 ORGANISATION

Requirement	Yes	No	Comments
IMPACT – VIC:	x		
Operational radiation protection (surveys, DIMR...):	x		Installation in high radiation environment must be done by taking the ALARA principle into account.

Radioactive storage of material:	x		Removed TCPC assembly should be considered as radioactive equipment (or put in a radioactive storage)
Radioactive waste:		x	
Fire risk/permit (IS41) (welding, grinding...):		x	
Alarms deactivation/activation (IS37):		x	
Others:			

7.2 REGULATORY TESTS

Requirement	Yes	No	Responsible Group	Comments
Pressure/leak tests:		X		
Electrical tests:	X		EN/STI	Standard controls tests for movement functionality.
Others:				

7.3 PARTICULAR RISKS

Requirement	Yes	No	Comments
Hazardous substances (chemicals, gas, asbestos...):		x	
Work at height:		x	
Confined space working:		x	
Noise:		x	
Cryogenic risks:		x	
Industrial X-ray (<i>tirs radio</i>):		x	
Ionizing radiation risks (radioactive components):		x	
Others:			

8. FOLLOW-UP OF ACTIONS BY THE TECHNICAL COORDINATION

Action	Done	Date	Comments
Carry out site activities:			

Carry out tests:			
Update layout drawings:			
Update equipment drawings:			
Update layout database:			
Update naming database:			
Update optics (MADX)			
Update procedures for maintenance and operations			
Update Safety File according to EDMS document 1177755 :			
Others:			

9. REFERENCES

[1] S. Montesano, J. Lendaro, F. Loprete, R. Losito, A. Masi, D. Mirarchi, S. Redaelli, W. Scandale, "Installation of the LUA9 Equipment in IR7 of the LHC", Engineering Change Request, LHC-TEC-EC-0001, [EDMS 1329235](#).

[2] S. Redaelli, *et al.*, "Installation in IR7 of Primary Crystal Collimators (TCPC) on Beam 2", LHC-TC-EC-0008, [EDMS 1714148](#).

[3] R. Rossi, presentation at the [97th ColUSM meeting](#) of Nov.24th, 2017.